

PLURALIZATION IN ARABIC AND ENGLISH: A CONTRASTIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

The present study is attempting to explore the plural markers in both Arabic and English. The data collected qualitatively are sorted to meet the scope of this paper. Through contrastive analysis, it is discovered that there are numerous significant differences rather than similarities in terms of syllable count start, patterns of plural nouns in relation to gender, regularity, regular vs irregular plural and internal vowel change. Moreover, Arabic has some uniqueness in its plural marking system. Being well informed on all of these might pave the way for second or foreign language learners to comprehensively understand the plural marking system in Arabic and English. This study consists of four chapters. In chapter one, the problem, the aims, the procedures, the hypotheses, the limit of the study and the value have been discussed. Chapter two shows the regular and irregular plurality in English language. Chapter Three discusses with regular and irregular plurality in Arabic language and its rules. Finally, the conclusion, suggestions and recommendations are mentioned in chapter four

Introduction:

1.1 The Problem:

The Arabic plural system, especially the irregular plural, is one of the most problematic parts of the language for the non-native students of Arabic, and they keep complaining about it all the time. On the other side, Arab students don't have this problem in general, because they learn most of this system from their spoken Arabic, which they learn passively (spontaneously or unsystematically) as they grow up and expand their vocabulary in schools where also they learn passively how to use written Arabic in speaking, (in my observations, I noticed that the Arab child until ten to twelve years he or she uses feminine plural –suffix –ات for most of the plurals). On the other hand, grammar books are not much help. Simply, because they are completely based on medieval- classical grammar books which did not pay enough attention to the plural system. The reason could be first; the system was well known to almost every Arab and probably looked natural. Second, that means it was not controversial part of the language or the grammar, and classical books cared most about literary controversies, language and dialectical debates particularly concerning poetry and Islamic heritage. In this game, the foreign student seems to be left helpless. As result, the books do not mention the plural system or they do, but too briefly, the Arabs including Arabic teachers offer no system about it (broken plural!), and the only available option is facing several years of collecting thousands of words through which one will be surprised by finding out this system very slowly and painfully.

Therefore, and in order to make it easy for non-native students to command this system in short time, I had to rely on my own efforts to a great extent and work hard to collect thousands of words in order to find out, classify, put together and systemize the rules of the “irregular plurals” and support them with long lists in which they become clear and easily accessible, putting into consideration the development of Modern Standard Arabic M.S.A. – in vocabulary- in the last two centuries and kinds of controversies it has created in the way i.e. you would find two Arabic teachers arguing fruitlessly for hours (like two clergymen from two different religions) about two plurals for the same word.

1.2 The Aims:

It is aimed at achieving the following objectives:

- Exploring the pluralization markers in English and Arabic language
- Showing the similarities and differences between the two languages in using pluralizations' markers.

1.3 The Hypotheses:

It hypothesized that:

- Both of English and Arabic language have regular and irregular patterns.
- The Arabic irregular plurals (broken plurals) are more frequent and have the exact patterns which sometimes can be explained through morpheme-based model and word-based model.

1.4 The Procedures:

The study adopts the following steps:

- Presenting a theoretical account regarding the concept of pluralization and the types of pluralization in English and Arabic language.
- Presenting the rules of using plural markers in both languages and their functions with examples.

1.5 The Limit:

The study is limited to investigate pluralization in English and Arabic language .

1.6 The Value:

This study is expected to be significance for better understanding about pluralization in English and Arabic language and how are the markers used. Further, this study will be valuable to those interested in the fields of morphology, phonology and syntax.

Pluralization in English Language:

2.1 Introduction:

Understanding what contrastive linguistics and contrastive analysis is a paramount important prior to the discussion and analysis of plural markers in Arabic and English. Contrastive linguistic is ‘a sub-discipline concerned with the comparison of two or more languages or sub-systems of languages in order to determine both the differences and the similarities between them’ (Fisiak et al. 1978 cited in Fisiak, 1981, p.v.). Contrastive analysis in this article is defined as ‘to research about differences and similarities between a limited number of languages carried out for ‘its own shake’ (Willems, Defrancq, Coleman & Noel, 2003, p.1). Saeed and Fatihi (2011) argue that contrastive analysis does help the translator and L2 in avoiding errors, solving the difficulties and minimizing interference, for it affords certain views, assumptions, explanations of some phenomena, such as creolisation and pidginisation of languages that are expected to assist the better bilingualism understanding. In simple way, contrastive analysis endeavors to see how “the same thing” can be said in other ways.

This morphological issue has grabbed some previous researchers’ attention. McCarthy and Prince (1999) have carried out research relating to the broken plural in Arabic, in which they do not only provide the issues about the Arabic broken plural in morphological aspect but also attempt to interconnect between morphology and phonology.

Approximately a decade later, Haspelmath and Sims (2010) state that there are two morphological rules: concatenative and non-concatenative. When the words can be described through the morpheme-based model, these are going to be the concatenative rule. Whereas, when the words are not possible to be described through the morpheme-based model because it has zero-affix, internal change or others, it must belong to the non-concatenative rules approachable through word- based model. These universal morphological rules to plural either in Arabic and English have the regular and irregular forms. Therefore, those similarities and differences are worth investigating.

The contrastive analysis specifically on morphological analysis about inflectional morpheme has also been done. Saeed and Fatihi (2011) compared two systems of the inflectional affixes in Arabic and English. This study was focused on the inflectional affixes of verbs, plural nouns, adjectives, and genitive of nouns on these two languages. The study reveals seven areas of similarities and differences e.g. no gender and dual suffix in English while there is gender and there are dual affixes in Arabic.

In 2012, Jassem has specifically carried out research on the plural and gender markers of English and Arabic as well as German, French, and Latin. Through the analysis genetic relationship using lexical root theory, he claims that Arabic personal pronoun is the origin of other languages

2.2 Plurality in English:

English has two number classes: singular and plural. Basically, in English, a noun which expresses more than one is simply called as plural noun. In this case, English plural nouns have two forms, regular and irregular (Azar, 1999).

2.2.1 English Regular Plural:

The regular form commonly occurs rather than the irregular. In regular plural form, inflectional plural morphemes, such as –s and –es are attached to the singular nouns (Fromkin Rodman, and Hyams, 2011). In this case, the researchers have found a simple way to know whether the noun is ended by –s or –es as in the following

Table 1: The criteria of plurals using –s or –es

Criteria		Examples	
	Nouns suffixes that end –sh, -ch, -s, -z ,and –x	Singular	Plural
		Brush	Brushes
		Watch	Watches
		Buzz	Buzzes
		Miss	Misses
		Fix	Fixes
	If a singular noun ends in- y and the letter before	Family	Families
	The -y is a consonant, change the ending to- ies to		
es	Make the noun plural		
		Half	Halves
	If the noun Final with- f or- fe, the f is often changed to- be before adding	Wife	Wives

	the -s to configure the plural version.		
	We also add the plural suffix –es to the majority of words ending in -o.	Volcano	Volcanoes
		Zero	Zeroes
	There are a few nouns that end in –o	Jumbo	Jumbos
		Silo	Silos
-S	There are a few nouns that end in –f	Chief	Chiefs
		Gulf	Gulfs
		Roof	Roofs
		Chef	Chefs

(Azar, 1999)

2.2.2 English Irregular Plur:

Compared to the regular form, the irregular plural form is more complex. Its inflectional suffix is unpredictable as in the case of the regular form. Irregular plural form might employ some suffixes other than –es or -s, internal stem change, and occasionally does not exhibit any suffix (Lieber, 2009).

The suffixes attached in the irregular nouns are like –i, –ae, and –a, borrowed from Latin and Greek. For instance, *fungus-fungi*, *vertebra-vertebrae*, and *bacterium-bacteria* (Carstairs, 2002). Usually, these borrowed inflectional suffixes are attached to the borrowed English nouns as well. The suffix –(r)en also occurs yet solely in some English words, such as, *ox-oxen*, and *child-children*, *brother-brethren* (Azar, 1999; Carstairs, 2002; Jassem, 2013).

The internal system change in plural form can be seen in the example *tooth-teeth*, *man-men*, and *mouse-mice*. It exhibits the allomorph of the root with different vowels from the singular which is also termed as ablaut (Spencer, 1994; Watson, 2002). Nevertheless, there are also some plural nouns which employ neither suffix nor vowel change, such as, *sheep*, *deer*, *fish*, and *trout*. This unchanged plural form is termed as zero-suffix (Carstairs, 2002).

In conclusion, the irregular plural form is exclusion to the English inflectional rule of plural formation. The term given to this phenomenon is *suppletion* (Carstairs, 2002; Fromkin, Rodman, and Hyams, 2011). The irregular plurals in English form closed classes, which constitute a fixed list from which particular forms can be lost, yet new forms cannot be added. On the contrary, the regular plural forms are considered default endings which mean when new nouns are added into English, it is simply attached by –s or –es, such as *vuvuzela* becomes *vuvuzelas* (Lieber, 2009).

Pluralization in Arabic Language:

3.1 Plurality in Arabic:

Unlike English number classifications which are divided into singular and plural, Arabic number class is categorized into three: singular, dual, and plural (Ryding, 2005). Thus, the Arabic plural starts from the count of three. As well as English plural, Arabic plural is classified into regular and broken (irregular) (Al- Ghalayini, 2011).

3.1.1 Arabic Regular Plural:

To form the Arabic regular plural, the stem must be free from any additional letter. And it must be noted that the stem (*wazan*) of an Arabic word consists of three letters *hijaiyyah*, which are commonly represented with ل, ع, ف. Every Arabic noun or adjective has a gender: masculine and feminine. Therefore, they employ different inflectional suffixes to form the plurals and usually do not have any internal change (McCarthy and Prince, 1999).

3.1.1.1 Arabic Masculine Regular Plural (Jama' Muthakkar Saalim):

Al-Ghalayani (2011) states that those employable nouns in masculine regular plurals are the sensible masculine proper nouns, whose bases do not end in [t], and the sensible masculine adjectives. For masculine regular form, the suffixes attached are –*uuna* (ون) when the nouns are in *rafa'* (nominative case) position while –*iina* (ين) is added when the nouns are in *nashab* (accusative case) and *jaar* (genitive case). The examples and detail explanations are provided in the subsequent table;

Table 2: The affixes in Arabic masculine regular plural

Affixes	Location	Meanings	Examples
	The topic	The believers came To the mosque	حضر المؤمنون الى المسجد
	An equational sentence's subject and predicate khabar	Believers are Patient	المؤمنون صابرون
-Uuna ون	The entry of kaana and its sisters	The journalists Are selling the Issues	الصحفيون يبيعون
	Enter Anne and her sisters	The students are diligent	إن الطلاب مجتهدون
	In the case of accusation	They got to school Late	دخلوا المدرسة متأخرين

Inna بن	Zanna and its sisters' subject and predicate	I believe the travellers (are) going to Mecca	أظن المسافرين ذاهبين إلى مكة
	The topic of inna and her sisters	Hey travellers come Back	ليت المسافرين يعودون
	The predicate of Kaana	The players were	كان اللاعبون نشيطين
Active	The target of Preposition.	I went with the Engineers to the Project	ذهبت مع المهندسين الى المشروع

If *manqush* or *mamdud*, *maqshur* of the form in not are words which the in employed are Those rules follows are as formulae eht ,("hamzah" in the form of isthe last letter of a word) *mamdud* the words are

- When there is a sensible masculine noun in the form of feminine noun which ends in "ء", the "ء" is turned into "و" such as, ورقاء (*waraqaa*) comes to be ورقاؤون (*waraqawuuna*).
- The suffix *-uuna* (ون) is attached if the "ء" is original. For instance, ورقاء (*waraqaa*) becomes ورقاؤون (*waraqawuuna*).
- When "ء" replaces ya' (ي) or wawu (و), its plural form can be directly attached with *-uuna* (ون) or the "ء" is substituted with و. For example, the word رجاء (*raja*) can be either رجاؤون (*rajaawuun*) or رجاؤون (*rajaawuun*).

When the word which ends in *alif* is found whether *layyinah* (ى) or not (!) (it is simply called *maqshur*), the ى or ا is omitted yet it still maintains the *fatha* "َ" (short vowel [a] above the letter). Consequently, if it is attached with ون – or – بن, it will be pronounced as *-auna* in *rafa'* or *-aina* in *nashab* and *jaar* as like the word مصطفى (مصطفى) (*mustafa*) is pluralized into مصطفىون (*mustafauna*) or مصطفىين (*mustafaina*).

However, if a word ends in ya' (ي), its plural is formed by omitting the ي and the last letter before ون – is given damma "ُ" (short vowel [u] above the letter), such as قاضي (*qaadhii*) converts into قاضون (*qaadh uuna*). On the other hand, if the inflectional morpheme is بن – , the kasra "ِ" is placed in the last letter, for example, قاضي becomes قاضين

(Al Ghalayini, 2011).

The preceding rules are applied when the nouns are not as the first term of an *idhaafa*. Nevertheless, if all these masculine regular plurals are placed as the first term of an *idhaafa* construction, the syllable na of the plural masculine disappears whether it is in the form of *rafa'*, *nashab*, or *jaar* (Abu Chacra, 2007).

For instance:

- Sound masculine plural normative: معلمو المدرسة (معلمون + المدرسة)
- Sound masculine plural accusative and genitive: معلمي المدرسة (معلمين + المدرسة)

3.1.1.2 Arabic Feminine Regular Plural (Jama' Muannats Saalim):

This type of plural commonly occurs and applies to a wide ranging of Arabic noun classes, human and nonhuman, and adjectives as well. To form the regular feminine plurals is by adding the suffix *aat* (ات -). Yet, it must be noticed that when the stem has *taa' marbuta* (ة -), the suffix substitutes the *taa' marbuta* (ة -) (Ryiding, 2005), for instance, قوّة (*quwwa* power) converts to قووات (*quwwaat*: powers)

Al Ghalayani (2011) states that this plural transpires in one of these subsequent criteria:

- Feminine proper nouns () 'almns., هندات □ هندات (Hindun □ Hinduns), فاطمة □ فاطمات (Fatima □ Fatimas)
- The nouns whose last letter is *taa' marbuta* (ة -) e.g. شجرة (*syajara*: tree) □ شجرات (*syajaraat*)
- The feminine adjectives which end in *taa' marbuta* (ة -) e.g. جميلة (*jamiila*: the beautiful one) □ جميلات (*jamiilaat*: the beautiful ones), and the feminine adjectives for comparative and superlative (ism tafdhil) such as, فضلى (*fudhla*: more/most prominent "singular") □ فضليات (*fudhlayaat*: more/most prominent "plural")
- The adjectives of the nonhuman masculine nouns e.g. حصان سابق (*hisaan saabiq*: racing horse) □ حصن سابقات (*hushaan saabiqaat*: racing horses)
- The verbal nouns (*mashdar*) which exceed three Arabic letters e.g. تعريف (*ta'riif*: definition) □ تعريفات (*ta'riifaat*)
- The diminutive (*tashghiiir*) of nonhuman masculine nouns e.g. دراهم (*duraihim*: dirham) □ دراهيمات (*duraihimaat*)
- The nouns or adjectives whose last letter is *alif ta'nits* (*mamduudah* (اء -) e.g. صحراء (*shahraa'*: desert) □ صحروات (*shahrawaat*)
- The nouns or adjectives which end with *alif ta'nits* (*maqshuroh* (ى -) e. مستشفى (*mustashfa*: hospital) □ مستشفيات (*mustashfaayat*)
- The words *ابن* or *ذي* which is positioned before the nonhuman nouns, e.g. المسكن نوات (*thawaat al maskan*: owners of house)
- The borrowed words which have not been established or determined their plural patterns e.g. تلغراف (*tilghraaf*: telegraph) □ تلغرافات (*tilghraafaat*: telegraphs)

Unlike the masculine regular plural which employs the different inflectional morpheme when they are no minative, accusative, or genitive, the feminine regular plural still employs the same suffix *aat* (ات -), but the sound ending takes *kasra* [i] as the nouns are either genitive or accusative, or *damma* [u] when the nouns are nominative.

(Ryding, 2005).

For further elucidation, see the following table:

Table 3: Arabic Feminine Regular Plural Affixes

Affixes	Location	Meanings	Examples
Aatu ات	The topic	Mothers are first Favourites	الأمهات أولات فضل
	of beginner and the news Entry	The students are Hardworking	الطالبات مجتهدا ت
	The entry of kaana and its sisters	The women Are still Dominated	لا تزال العتيقات إماء
	Entry Inna and her sisters	The female workers are patient	إن العاملات صابرات
Aati_	The target of a Transitive verb	My father Established the Companies	أسس أبي الشركات
	In the case of accusative	The teachers entered the administration	دخلت المدرسات الإدارة متاخرات
	The topic and Predicate of Zanna And its sisters	I believe the female students are busy	أظن الطبيبات مشغولات
	Sisters The topic of Inna and its	May the enmities end	ليت العداوات تنتهي
	The entry of kaana and its sisters	The libraries are Large	كانت المكتبات كبيرات
	Vocative first term of Construct (Nida')	O Flowers	يازهراوات
	. The target of Preposition	This school is one of the scientific schools	هذه المدرسة من المدارس العلمية
	The target of Locative verb	I stood up in front of the (female)	وقفت أمام الطالبات

in the (There are some exceptional procedures to arrange the Arabic regular plural. If the nouns own hamza and is last letter mamduud), the hamza is treated like forming duality in Arabic. Thus, the hamza can be omitted or keep the existence of hamza . Then the suffix *aat* is attached like the following (altered with *waawu*) :examples

– صحراء صحراوات a. Desert deserts Shahraa' shahraw aat

– قراء قراءات b. Reader readers Qurraa' qurraa' aat

– (maqshuurah (- the noun s possess alif layyinah As well as mamdud , if

the alif layyinah is treated like forming duality in Arabic. Consequently, the alif

For . (or *waawu*) layyinah is replaced with *ya'*

- هدى هديات a. Direction directions Hudaa hudaay aat

- زكاة زكوات akat zakawaatb. Tithe tithes Z

From the above elaboration, it is known that to form the Arabic feminine regular plural is done by attaching the suffix. However, if the basic form's middle letter of the singular noun consists of *sukun* , which represents the is not merely attached. It is a must to change that *sukun* into another (existence of a vowel, the suffix *aatnon*). (diacritical mark (*harakat* In this circumstance, Al Ghalayani (2011) says that there are several ways to change the diacritical marks.

1. The nouns which possess *fatha* in its first letter should change the second

prostrations Sajdatun -letter's mark into fatha as well. For example: Prostration

سجدة : سجادات sajad aatun

When the first letter possesses damma , the second letter .2

y damma as well as the first leta. Emp lo

b. Employ fatha

c. Keep the existence of sukuun

Thus, the word

خطوة can be خطوات

3.1.1.3 Broken Plural in Arabic (Jama' Taksiir):

Soudi et al (2007), cited in Saeed and Fatihi (2011), says, "The Arabic broken plural system is highly allomorphic". It is known that this plural type involves the vowel pattern shift within the word stem, such as the English words, man men, foot feet, or tooth teeth (McCarthy and Prince, (1999) and Ryding, 2005).

Though, it sometimes might involve the affixation of extra consonant, which are

Commonly hamza or waaw. Al Ghalayani (2011) also states that reduction of the letters happens in forming the Arabic broken plural. Unlike the English irregular plural which rarely occur s, the Arabic broken plurals (irregular) are frequently and mostly used (Abu Chacra, 2007).

In this case, unlike the English irregular plurals which do not possess any exact pattern, the Arabic has numerous strict rules to form this plural type. The pattern will be symbolized by C for representing the consonant, V for vowel, and VV for long vowel. Ryding (2005) has classified the patterns in accordance with the vowel change of the words and affixation into:

(1) Broken plural patterns which employ the sole internal vowel change

(1.1) Plural CuCuuC (فُعْل ع ف 'uul) is from singular singular:

1. CaCiC (فاعل 'il), e.

Spleen/s Kabid/kubuud

كَبِد / كَبِد

2. CaCC (فاعل 'l whose the middle letter is not waaw e.g.

Liver/s Qalb/quluub

قَلْب / قَلْب

3. CiCC fi'l (فاعل 'l), e.

Elephant/s Fiil/fuyuuul

فَيْل / فَيْل

4. CuCC fi'l (فاعل 'l), whose second and third hijaiyyah letters are not alif,

waaw, or ya. e.g.

Army/ies

Jund/junuud /جُنْد /جُنْد

(1.2) Plural CuCCaaC (فاعل 'aal) belongs to singular CaaCiC (faa'il), whose last letter is not alif, waaw, or ya . For

Writer/s

Kaatib/kuttaab

كُتَاب / كُتَاب

(1.3) Plural CiCaaC (fi'aal) belongs to

1. CaCC (فاعل 'l), which does not have ya in the second letter, e.g. Clo

the/s Tsaub/tsiyaab

2. CaCaC (فاعل 'al), e.g. whose second hijaiyyah letters are not alif,

waaw, or ya , or which is not mudha'af , e.

Mountain/s

Jabal/jibaaal

جَبَل / جَبَل

3. CiCC

fi'l (فاعل 'l), e.g.

Well/s

Bi'r/bi'aar

بَيْر / بَيْر

4. CuCC (فاعل 'l), whose second letter is not waaw and third letter is not

ya, e.g.

Arrow/s

Rumh/rimaah

رُمح / رُمح

5. CaCiiC (فاعل 'iil), whose third hijaiyyah letters are not alif, waaw, or

ya, e.g.

The sick/sicks
Mariidh/miraadh

مرضى /مريض

6. CaCCaaC, Ca CCa, CaCCaaCah (fa'laan, fa'la, fa'laanah/fu'laanah fu'laanah, e.

The thirsty

one/s

'athsyaan, 'athsya,

'athsyaanah/ 'ithaasy

شئى، عطشاً، عطشاً

ش عطاشة/عطشاً

(1.4) Plural CuCaC (fu'al فع ل) is from 1. CuCCah (fu'la hh لة فع), e.

Room/s

Ghurfaah/ghuraf

رف غ /ة غرف

2. CuCCa (fu'la), e.

Small one/s

Shughra/shughar

ر صنع /رى صنع

(1.5) Plural CuCuC (fu'ul فع ل) is specialized to

1. CaCuC (fa'uul فع ل), which functions as doer, e.

Jealous one/s Ghayuur/ghuyur

ر غى /ؤر غى

2. CiCaaC (fi'aal فع ل), e.

Book/s

Kitaab/kutub

ب كت /ب كتا

(1.6) Plural CiCaC (fi'al) is from singular CiCCah fi'lah). For

Piece/s

Qith'ah/qitha'

قطعة / قِطْع

(1.7) Plural CaCCaa (fa'laa فعلى) is from singular CaCiiC fa'iil (فعيل). For example:

Dead

Mayyit/mawtaa

موتى /ميت

(2) Broken plural patterns involving both vowel change and affixation of consonant

(2.1) Some of Plural of paucity (jam' qillah) patterns: aCCuC af'ul) and CiCCah fi'lah) are considered to be applied in the assortment of three to ten substances.

For instance:

a. River/s Nahr/anhur

أنهار /نهر

b. Youth/s Fata/fitya

فتية /فتى

The singular CaCC (fa'l), CaCaC fa'al), or hollow ajwaf): CVVC faal, fuul, fiil) are pluralized into jam' qillah aCCaaC (af'aal). It indicates that this formation involves hamza with fatha to the stem and the alteration of vowel pattern to a long / aa / between the second and third base. For

a. House/s

Bait/abyaat

b. Uncle/s Khaal/akhwaal

أخوال /خال

c. Door/s Baab/abwaab

There are numerous borrowed words fitting this pattern, such as:

a. Film/s

Film/aflaam

أفلام /فلم

b. Mile/s Miil/amyaaal

أميال /ميل

(2.2)

Suffixation of nuun in plural CVCCaan (fa'laan/fu'laan/ fi'laan), whose plural is fa'iil, fa'al, and fa'l for instance:

a. Neighbor/s

Jaar/jiiraan

جيران/جار

b. Grass/es Khasyab/khusybaan

خشبان/خشب

(2.3)

Taa' marbuutha is suffixed as the part of plural pattern. However, it does not imply the feminine gender. (2.3.1) CaCaaCiCah (fa'aalilah) functions as the plural of names of groups or profession borrowed from other languages:

Philosopher/s

Faylusuuf/falaasifah

فلاسفة/فيلوسوف

(2.3.2) Plural CaaCa is applied as the plural of nouns derived from hollow verbs:

Leader/s

Qaa'id/qaadah

قادة/قائد

(2.3.3) The active

participles derived from defective verbs (fi'l naaqish) are pluralized into CuCaat (fu'aat

Reciter/s

Raawin/ruwaat

رواة/راو

(2.3.4) The singular CaaCiC is turned into plural CaCaCah (fa'alah) which often alternates with CuCCaaC.

Servant/s

Khaadim/khada

ma khuddam - خدام خدمة/خادم

(2.3.5) Plural aCCiCah (af'ilah) goes to singular CVCaaCfa'aal and fi'aal). It

can be simply recognized that this plural owns prefix hamza and suffix taa' marbutah . This form includes in jam' qillah as well For example:

Ans wer/s Jawaab/ajwibah

أجوبة/جواب

(2.3.6) Plural CaCaayaa (fa'aayaa) is used for certain feminine nouns, specifically the hamzated nouns. This type is inflexible and always ends with alif .

Corner

Zaawiyah/zawaayaa

زاوية/زاويات From the preceding patterns

, it must be highlighted that there are two

kinds of broken plural: jam' qillah referring to the nouns among three till ten, and jam' katsroh applied to the above of ten items. In jam' katsroh , shighat muntaha al jumu' is recognized , refer ring to all plural forms that are suffixed to two or three hijaiyyah letters, in which sukuun is placed over the middle letter (Al Ghalayani, 2011). There are nineteen forms of shighat muntaha al jumu'

Table 4: Forms of shighat muntaha al jumu'

Patterns	Singulars	Plurals
فعالل	سفرجل	سفارج
فعاليل	فردوس	فراديس
أفاعل	أفضل	أفاضل
أفاعيل	إضبارة	أضابير
تفاعل	تجربة	تجارب
تفاعيل	تسبيح	تسابيح
مفاعل	مسجد	مساجد
مفاعيل	ميثاق	موثاق
فواعل	جوه	جواهر
فواعيل	ساطر	سواطير

Plurals

:The following are some interesting facts about broken plurals in Arabic

1. Plurals of the plurals-

: This type usually has a conventional plural suffix or is broken plural. For instance

-Hands.

1-Houses- اي د / ايادي

بيوت/ايبات

Plurals that don't have a singular form.²

:This occurs when the singular form no longer exists or is forgotten

تعاجي ب .Wonders

roots that have been altered Plurals derived from-3

مرأة/نساء .Women

for example, the word fulk "في الفلك المشحون" Plurals that sometimes mean singular occur in the Koran .In verse-4 denotes singularity, whereas

"والفلك التي تجرى في البحر" denotes plurality

If the nouns are nominative, the final letter should be diacritically marked with da mma () .If the nouns are in .the genitive case, kasra () is used as the final letter

a () should be placed above the final letter (Hamid. 1994). Consider the following When accusative is used, fath :example

Table 5: The position of diacritical mark in Arabic broken plural

Positions	Examples	Meanings
Nominative	بناء المدارس في تلك المدينة	city Build schools in that
Genitive	صفوف طلاب نظيفة	Clean classrooms
Accusative	ذلك الحوار ينتج حقائق كثيرة	This dialogue produces many facts

4.1 Conclusion:

It is found that English plurals start from the count of two while Arabic plurals start from the count of three. Both of these languages also have regular and irregular patterns. Unlike English, the Arabic irregular plurals (broken plurals) are more frequent and have the exact patterns which sometimes can be explained through morpheme-based model and word-based model. The affixation of regular plural in Arabic also engages the gender, such as *-iina* or *-uuna* for masculine plural and *-aat* for feminine. It is also found that the English plural marking occurs solely in nouns. On the other hand, nouns and adjectives become the object of Arabic regular and irregular plural marking. The Arabic broken plural pattern sometimes solely employs the internal vowel change which might involve both vowel change and affixation of consonant. Some unique facts of plurality in Arabic occur such as: plurals of the plurals, plurals not having the singular form, plurals from modified roots, plural form which means singular and one noun which can be pluralized into regular and irregular form. Based on the comparison, it can be argued that the plural marking system in both languages is dissimilar rather than parallel. Structurally, Arabic plural marking system is more complex rather than English. Thus, L2 or FL learners may find English plural markers easier to learn than Arabic.

4.2 Suggestions for Further Studies:

- Conducting functional grammar using pluralization in Arabic.
- Conducting irregular and regular plurality in Arabic dialect of Iraq.

4.3 Recommendations:

It is recommended that:

Eclectic rules should be adopted so as to fulfill the whole requirements of comparison between the two languages.

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